

CoARA Action Plan

The Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of the Valencian Community (Fisabio) is a non-profit scientific organisation whose primary goal is to promote, support, disseminate, develop, and implement scientific-technical research and healthcare and biomedical innovation within the Valencian Community.

Fisabio operates across the Valencian Community, integrating and managing R&D&I activities carried out at Fisabio-Public Health (Fisabio-SP) and Fisabio-Health Departments (Fisabio-DS). Fisabio-DS covers 19 out of the 24 Health Departments of the Valencian Community (including their respective referral hospitals, primary care centres, and public health centres), the Valencian Community Blood Transfusion Center, and five Hospitals for Chronic and Long-Term Care (HACLE).

Fisabio provides services to researchers in the Valencian healthcare network, specialists working on research and innovation projects, and clinical studies managed through the Foundation. Additionally, Fisabio coordinates the Valencian Biobank Network.

Membership in CoARA

Fisabio has been a member of CoARA since June 2024, when its membership was formalised. However, the working group established for this purpose had already been working on defining the milestones and tasks included in the action plan attached at the end of this document.

By joining CoARA, Fisabio is committed to reforming research evaluation practices to recognise the diverse outcomes, practices, and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. This commitment entails the formulation of evaluation criteria and processes that prioritise quality, impact, diversity, inclusion, and collaboration.

Involvement of the Scientific Community in the Change Process

The involvement of the scientific community in the change process is considered to be of crucial importance by Fisabio. Consequently, the entity's action plan must be developed with full consideration for the voices, experiences, and perspectives of the research groups affiliated with Fisabio.

Their involvement is vital for ensuring that the actions outlined in this document lead to the expected success and guarantee the full transformation of research evaluation at Fisabio.

Action Plan

This document contains the action plan designed as a roadmap for the period between 2026 and 2029.

This document was updated following the feedback gathered after launching a global survey of the research staff at Fisabio. The commitments and priority lines of work were further specified after a co-creation session with research and management staff of the foundation.

This document was prepared by the working group created for this purpose, taking into account the guidelines set out in the document *Support for CoARA signatories in the preparation of Action Plans*. In addition, the action plan has been reviewed and validated by different internal stakeholder groups within the organization.

As indicated in the document itself, the action plan will be reviewed and updated on an annual basis. Any changes made, as well as the milestones achieved, will be communicated internally to all collaborators of FISABIO.

The following table shows the planned actions in accordance with the commitments undertaken following the signing of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment.

CoARA commitment	Line of action	Associated tasks	Deadline	Action Lead	Progress
Commitment 1: Recognise the diversity of contributions to and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.	Identify all the research practices carried out in Fisabio	Survey to researchers	2026	COARA Working Group	
		Construction of a map of diversity of contributions	2026	COARA Working Group	
		Validation by the agents involved	2026	COARA Working Group	
Commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.	Review diversification in evaluation standards	Search and locate agents (evaluation agencies, research groups, etc.) that work on alternative indicators and qualitative metrics	2026	COARA Working Group	
		Identify valid indicators according to research practice	2026	COARA Working Group	
		Associate indicators with research practices	2027	COARA Working Group	
		Open Discussion Forum among FISABIO Researchers on the application of COARA P	2026	COARA Working Group	
	Introduction to portfolio / narrative CV	Development of guidelines for the committee on how to evaluate narratives fairly and consistently	2026	COARA Working Group	
		Creation of a review structure template	2026	COARA Working Group	
		Development of internal guidance on the responsible use of metrics	2027	COARA Working Group	
Commitment 5: Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to.	Definition and monitoring of the Action Plan after signing the COARA Agreement	Creation of the CoARA working group at Fisabio,	2026	Executive management	
		Action Plan Definition	2025	COARA Working Group	
		Review and publication of the first version of the Action Plan	2026	COARA Working Group	
		Preparation of the annual Action Plan Monitoring Report	Annual	COARA Working Group	
		Action Plan Update	as needed	COARA Working Group	
	Incentive system definition	Drafting of the monitoring report at the end of the Action Plan	2029	COARA Working Group	
		Design a quality seal for groups aligned with responsible evaluation	2028	COARA Working Group	
		Propose awards and data champions	2028	COARA Working Group	
Commitment 6: Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes.	Review and update of criteria for internal calls (UNISALUT) and the accreditation of FISABIO research groups	Update internal calls. Review the prioritization of criteria for internal calls	2026-2027	COARA Working Group	
	Assessment of evaluation criteria for research staff (individual classification)	Update criteria for the accreditation of research groups	2026-2027	COARA Working Group	
		Update criteria for the evaluation of research staff	2026-2027	COARA Working Group	
Commitment 7: Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.	Open Science training for researchers	Specific training about peer-review good practices	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	
		Specific training on new (alternative) metrics	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	
		Specific training on narrative CV	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	
		Training about open science publication	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	
	Development of support documentation	Writing guides, protocols, recommendations	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	
		Writing the communication plan	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	
		Implementing activities described in the communication plan: training activities, meetings, seminars, workshops, etc.	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	
Commitment 8: Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.	Good practices sharing with similar institutions	Developing synergies and joint projects with research foundations and institutes	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	
	External sharing	COARA Spanish Chapter participation	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	
		Different working groups participation	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	
Commitment 9: Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.	Periodic updates on the progress of the Action Plan	Elaborate an Action Plan to disseminate the updates of the adherence through various channels	2026	COARA Working Group	
		Publish a press release to inform on the adherence and next steps	2025	COARA Working Group	
		Social Media coverage of the developings of the activities in this Action Plan (#CoARA)	2025-2028	COARA Working Group	
		Publish Action Plan progress in the FISABIO Annual Report	Annual	COARA Working Group	
		Publish a press release to inform on updates regarding the implementation of the commitments	2026	COARA Working Group	
		Inform on the progress at scientific/academic events to obtain feedback and increase the project's visibility	2026-2027	COARA Working Group	
		Prepare a survey to obtain feedback and increase the project's visibility	2025	COARA Working Group	
		Annually update the Action Plan	Annual	COARA Working Group	
		Publish a press release to communicate achieved milestones	2029	COARA Working Group	
		Communicate achieved milestones internally	2026-2029	COARA Working Group	